

Densities, excess molar volumes, viscosities of binary mixtures of ethanediol with water at various temperatures

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Experimental values of density, viscosity for the binary mixtures of ethanediol with water are presented at five different temperatures (298.15–318.15 K) over the entire mole fraction range of the mixture components at atmospheric pressures. From these data, excess molar volume, deviation in viscosity of the compositions have been calculated. Negative values of excess molar volumes are exhibited by the systems. The results suggest that weak hydrophobic interaction might be developed in the water rich region, and its magnitude increases at low temperatures. The Redlich-Kister relation is used to estimate the binary interaction parameters which are in satisfactory agreement with the experimental data.

Thermodynamic properties of various alcohols have been studied in numerous solvents¹⁻³. Ethanediol is a widely used solvent for industrial processes⁴. Therefore, thermodynamic study pertaining to ethanediol is desirable for many applications. Hence, the study of binary mixture of ethanediol + water compositions was undertaken.

Density and viscosity of binary liquid mixtures of ethanediol + water were measured in the temperature range 298.15–318.15 K with an interval of 5 K at atmospheric pressure. Excess molar volumes, deviation in viscosity are calculated and correlated by polynomial expressions. The aim of this work is to provide information regarding the molecular interactions between ethanediol and water using excess molar volumes and deviations in viscosity.

Results and Discussion

The excess molar volumes (V^E) were calculated from the density measurement⁵ by the relationship,

$$\rho = \frac{x_1 M_1 + x_2 M_2}{x_1 V_1 + x_2 V_2 + V^E} \quad (1)$$

where x_1 and x_2 are mole fractions, M_1 and M_2 the molecular weights and V_1 and V_2 the molar volumes of ethanediol (1) and water (2), respectively. The experimental densities, excess molar volumes, viscosities and deviation in viscosity of binary mixtures of ethanediol (1) + water (2) at five different temperatures are listed in Table 1.

The excess molar volume were correlated by Redlich-Kister equation^{6,7},

$$V^E = x_1 x_2 \sum a_i (x_1 - x_2)^i \quad (2)$$

The coefficient in eqn. (2) was estimated by the least-squares fit method, where the squares of the difference be-

tween the calculated and experimental excess molar volumes results is minimized. The optimal values of the coefficients in eqn. (2) are listed in Table 2. The standard deviation was calculated⁷ by

$$\sigma(V^E) = [\sum(V_{\text{expt}}^E - V_{\text{cal}}^E)^2 / (D - N)]^{0.5} \quad (3)$$

where D and N are the number of data points and parameters, respectively. It is observed that the average standard deviation at all temperatures is about $0.034 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$.

The graphical presentation of the excess molar volumes is shown in Fig. 1. It shows that V^E is negative over the entire range of composition at all measured temperatures. Maximum deviation in the excess molar volumes occurs at 0.4 mole fraction. Maximum negative^{1,8} values of excess molar volume in this temperature range is about $0.39 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$. These large negative values of V^E arise due to in-

Fig. 1. Excess molar volumes (V^E) for the system ethanediol (1) + water (2) from 298.15 to 318.15 K

Table 1. Densities, viscosities, excess molar volumes and viscosity deviation of ethanediol (1) + water (2)

x_1	ρ (g cm ⁻³)	η (mPa.s)	V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta\eta$ (mPa.s)
		298.15 K		
0.0000	0.997145	0.8903	0.0000	0.0000
0.0312	1.009700	1.1269	-0.0447	-0.3592
0.0676	1.022679	1.4319	-0.0986	-0.5117
0.1106	1.035939	1.8549	-0.1607	-0.8684
0.1621	1.048895	2.3980	-0.2205	-1.1277
0.2249	1.061900	3.1553	-0.2866	-1.3489
0.3033	1.073328	4.1641	-0.3171	-1.5617
0.4037	1.084536	5.6182	-0.3423	-1.6720
0.5372	1.094353	7.8189	-0.3189	-1.5514
0.7231	1.102743	11.2183	-0.2207	-0.9388
1.0000	1.109783	16.4716	0.00000	0.0000
		303.15 K		
0.0000	0.995741	0.7973	0.0000	0.0000
0.0312	1.008057	1.0071	-0.0436	-0.1705
0.0676	1.020731	1.2487	-0.0952	-0.3725
0.1106	1.033659	1.5770	-0.1543	-0.5676
0.1621	1.046289	2.0160	-0.2109	-0.7570
0.2249	1.059020	2.6200	-0.2748	-0.9184
0.3033	1.070240	3.4380	-0.3044	-1.0560
0.4037	1.081251	4.6030	-0.3289	-1.1147
0.5372	1.090943	6.3169	-0.3070	-1.0279
0.7231	1.099265	9.0281	-0.2130	-0.5825
1.0000	1.106271	12.9856	0.0000	0.0000
		308.15 K		
0.0000	0.994142	0.7910	0.0000	0.0000
0.0312	1.006215	0.8642	-0.0422	-0.1590
0.0676	1.018618	1.0775	-0.0918	-0.3007
0.1106	1.031249	1.3706	-0.1483	-0.4267
0.1621	1.043593	1.7372	-0.2022	-0.5624
0.2249	1.056067	2.2449	-0.2640	-0.6671
0.3033	1.067068	2.9060	-0.2919	-0.7705
0.4037	1.077925	3.8950	-0.3165	-0.7605
0.5372	1.087506	5.2843	-0.2960	-0.6729
0.7231	1.095760	7.4127	-0.2056	-0.3572
1.0000	1.102749	10.4700	0.0000	0.0000
		313.15 K		
0.0000	0.992325	0.6526	0.0000	0.0000
0.0312	1.004197	0.8087	-0.0412	-0.1101
0.0676	1.016335	1.0248	-0.0890	-0.2046
0.1106	1.028714	1.2707	-0.1431	-0.3257
0.1621	1.040791	1.5880	-0.1945	-0.4478
0.2249	1.053030	2.0314	-0.2542	-0.5403
0.3033	1.063941	2.6182	-0.2836	-0.6225
0.4037	1.074543	3.4412	-0.3049	-0.6563
0.5372	1.084027	4.6638	-0.2858	-0.5729
0.7231	1.092234	6.4845	-0.1991	-0.3385
0000	1.099204	9.1859	0.0000	0.0000
		318.15 K		
0.0000	0.990321	0.5972	0.0000	0.0000
0.0312	1.002009	0.7291	-0.0404	-0.0895
0.0676	1.013942	0.8975	-0.0866	-0.1794
0.1106	1.026057	1.1126	-0.1385	-0.2695
0.1621	1.037889	1.3996	-0.1875	-0.3479
0.2249	1.049917	1.7728	-0.2454	-0.4204
0.3033	1.060697	2.2822	-0.2748	-0.4674
0.4037	1.071119	2.9840	-0.2946	-0.4781
0.5372	1.080516	3.9952	-0.2767	-0.4143
0.7231	1.088682	5.4956	-0.1932	-0.2331
1.0000	1.095639	7.6938	0.0000	0.0000

creased interactions⁸ between unlike molecules¹² or very large differences in the molar volume of pure components at low temperature. The V^E becomes more negative with decreasing temperature. It would appear that the temperature coefficient of V^E depends on the increase in molar volume of complex formation. The magnitude suggest that there is weak interaction of hydrophobic hydration between the polar hydroxyl group of the ethanediol and water.

Dynamic viscosities (η) of ethanediol (1) + water (2) mixtures at different temperatures are calculated by the measured density and flow time of the mixture and are listed in Table 1. The viscosity deviation was calculated by the equation,

Table 2. Regression results for the excess volumes of ethanediol (1) + water (2) mixtures at various temperatures

T K	a_0	a_1	a_2	σ cm ³ mol ⁻¹
298.15	-1.5552	0.8690	1.2273	0.035
303.15	-1.4951	0.8574	1.1872	0.034
308.15	-1.4389	0.8413	1.1564	0.034
313.15	-1.3905	0.8302	1.1262	0.033
318.15	-1.3461	0.8217	1.0961	0.033

$$\Delta\eta = \eta - \{x_1 \eta_1 + x_2 \eta_2\} \quad (5)$$

The experimental values of $\Delta\eta$ are also reported in Table 1. Viscosity deviation were also correlated by Redlich-Kister equation similar to eqn. (2),

$$Q = x_1 x_2 \sum H_i (x_1 - x_2)^i \quad (6)$$

where $Q = \Delta\eta$ (mPa.s). The coefficient in eqn. (6) are also regressed by employing the least-square fit method. Standard deviations for the viscosity calculations were determined by eqn. (7), similar to eqn. (3),

$$\sigma(\Delta\eta) = [\sum(\Delta\eta_{\text{exp}} - \Delta\eta_{\text{cal}})^2 / (D-N)]^{0.5} \quad (7)$$

The optimal parameters in correlating the deviation of viscosity are listed in Table 3.

Table 3. Regression results for the deviation of viscosity of ethanediol (1) + water (2) at various temperatures

T K	H_0	H_1	H_2	σ mPa.s
298.15	-7.3504	5.0829	1.3711	0.252
303.15	-4.9826	2.3599	2.2731	0.106
308.15	-3.5350	2.2906	1.0280	0.117
313.15	-2.8994	1.7018	1.3685	0.068
318.15	-2.2221	1.4427	1.0054	0.069

Graphical presentations of the experimental $\Delta\eta$ plotted against with the fitted curve are shown in Fig. 2. The $\Delta\eta$ is negative and its values decrease with increasing temperature⁹. The curves are skewed towards the water-rich region. An increased temperature is found to enhance the mixture

Fig. 2. Viscosity deviation for the system ethanediol (1) + water (2) from 298.15 to 318.15 K

viscosity contribution to the overall viscosity deviation. The binary system of ethanediol (1) + water (2) shows a maximum viscosity at x_1 around 0.4. This minimum point becomes more evident at lower temperature.

Experimental

Ethanediol (A.R., S.D Fine) was first dried over fused calcium oxide overnight and then distilled twice under vacuum. The middle fraction was further dried using 4A molecular sieves (Linde) and stored and protected against moisture and carbon dioxide. Triple-distilled water (specific conductance less than 10 S cm^{-1}) was employed in making of the compositions. All measurements of density and viscosity were carried out at room temperature ($293.15 \pm 1 \text{ K}$). The measured densities¹¹ and viscosities of pure ethanediol and water at 303.15 K are close to literature¹⁰ Liquid mixtures of various compositions were prepared by weight with an accuracy of $\pm 0.1 \text{ mg}$.

Densities of the pure components and their compositions were measured on a vibrating tube density meter (Anton Paar Model DMA 5000) measuring with high-test

accuracy ($\pm 0.001^\circ$) in wide temperature range

Viscosities were measured using a suspended level Cannon-Ubbelohde viscometer. The viscometer was suspended vertically in a constant temperature bath ($\pm 0.05^\circ$). The time given to attain thermal equilibrium for the content of viscometer was 15 min. The flow time was measured to an accuracy of 0.1 s till a constant flow time was observed. The viscometer was calibrated separately with benzene and toluene (HPLC grade). At 303.15 K, the reproducibility in the viscosity measurement was $\pm 0.01 \text{ mPa.s}$. Viscosities of the pure component of water were taken from the literature. From the densities and flow time, absolute viscosity of the mixtures and pure solvents were calculated using equation,

$$\eta_1/\eta_2 = \rho_1 t_1/\rho_2 t_2,$$

where the symbols have the usual meaning.

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